

A Study on Psychiatric Morbidity of Patients with ESRD Undergoing Hemodialysis

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Abstract:

Background: In CKD kidney is damaged in due course to a level that patient need regular dialysis. It put a lot of stress on dialysis patients. Multiple factors affect the mental health of CKD patients on hemodialysis. So this study tries to measures their level of anxiety and depression and study the associated factors.

Material and Methods: A cross sectional observational study was done among patients more that 18 years of age diagnosed as end stage renal disease on maintenance haemodialysis in department of General Medicine and Department of Nephrology, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College & Hospital, Jaipur. Socio-demographic factors , associated co-morbidities and dialysis related factors were noted and anxiety and depression level was measured using HAM-A scale and HAM-D scale respectively.

Results: In the study family income, family type, number of co-morbidities, duration of CKD and number of dialysis per week were all significantly related to HAM-A ($p < 0.01$) and HAM-D scale ($p < 0.01$) and there was no relationship of gender, residence, marital status and education level of CKD patients with HAM-A and HAM-D scale.

Conclusion: Economic and social support along with prompt treatment is needed to prevent anxiety and depression among CKD patients as low family income, number of co-morbidities, duration of CKD and number of dialysis per week may be risk factors for deterioration mental health of CKD patients.

Keywords: Anxiety, Depression, Mental health, Hemodialysis, End Stage Renal Disease.

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Introduction

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a disorder where the kidneys are damaged and unable to filter blood as effectively as they should. If therapy for chronic kidney disease (CKD) is not received, the condition can worsen over time and it may lead to End Stage Renal Disease (ESRD) that is managed by dialysis or kidney transplantation. [1] CKD affects more than 10% of the global population, or more than 800 million people. As risk factors including obesity and diabetes mellitus have increased, CKD patients have also increased in number. [2] The reported prevalence of CKD in different Indian regions ranges from <1% to 13%, and recently, data from the International Society of Nephrology's Kidney Disease Data Center Study reported a prevalence of 17%. [3,4] CKD patients not only suffer from biochemical abnormalities but also suffer from psychiatric problems leading to

extreme worry and anxiety somatic symptoms as palpitations, sweating, chest discomfort, and dread of death. [5-7]

Long-term dialysis treatment alone frequently leads to diminished or nonexistent financial income, a loss of independence, dependency on care givers, and disturbances in social, marital, and family life etc. [8] So there was a need to study the psychiatric morbidity of patients and know the factors affecting them and this study was done with following objectives:

(1) To evaluate psychiatric morbidity of patients with end stage renal disease undergoing maintenance hemodialysis

(2) To study the factors affecting the psychiatric morbidity of the study subjects

Materials and Methods

A cross sectional observational study was done among patients more than 18 years of age diagnosed as end stage renal disease on maintenance haemodialysis for a minimum of 3 months in department of General Medicine and Department of Nephrology, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College & Hospital, Jaipur. Ethical clearance was taken from institutional ethical committee. After taking due consent socio-demographic, disease details and detail about co-morbidities were noted. Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale (HAM-A) [9] was used to measure the level of anxiety among study subjects and Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HDRS/Ham-D) was used to measure the depression. The 14 items on the Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale (HAM-A), which gauges anxiety intensity, are each characterized by a set of symptoms which evaluates both physical and psychological anxiety. It has score range of 0–56 and each item is rated on a scale as per severity.⁹ HAM-D is related to depressive symptoms experienced in the previous week. A score of 0–7 on the HDRS17 is typically considered to be within the normal range, but a score of 20 or more is typically necessary to be admitted into a clinical study. [10]

Data compiled in MS Excel and analysis was done in SPSS version 16 and results were described using Chi square test and considered significant if p value found to be less than 0.05.

Results

Table 1: Distribution of study population according HAM-D and HAM-A Score

Variable	Frequency	Percent	Mean (SD)
HAM-D Scale			
Normal	24	24.0	14.10 (6.69)
Mild	30	30.0	
Moderate	13	13.0	
Severe	21	21.0	
Very Severe	12	12.0	
HAM-A Scale			
Mild	45	45.0	21.11 (12.73)
Mild to Moderate	16	16.0	
Moderate to Severe	11	11.0	
Severe to Very Severe	28	28.0	
Total	100	100.0	

As shown in the table according to HAM-D Scale 24(24%) were not suffering from any depression and rest 30(30%), 13(13%), 21(21%) and 12(12%) study subjects were suffering from mild, moderate, severe and very severe depression respectively with mean HAM-D score 14.10(SD 6.69). Similarly

In this study 100 CKD patients on hemodialysis were selected. The mean age of the study subject was 50.05 yrs (SD 10.32) with 65 (65%) males and 35 (35%) females with male to female ratio 1.86:1. In this study 83 (83%), 8 (8%), 4(4%) and 5(%) subjects were married, unmarried, divorcee and widower respectively and 66 (66%) subjects had their residence in rural area and rest 34(34%) had their residence in urban area. Educational level showed 15(15%), 47(47%), 25(25%) and 13(13%) were illiterate, attained education up-to primary level, secondary level and college level respectively. In this 52(52%) study subject lived in the nuclear family and 48(48%) lived in joint family. Regarding family income 35(35%), 37(37%), 13(13%) and 15(15%) of the study had family income < Rs 10000, 10001-50000, 50001-100000 and > 100000 respectively.

In this study most of the study subject i.e 35(35%) were suffering from two diseases i.e diabetes and hypertension and rest 7(7%) had no co-morbidity; 21(21%) were suffering from single disease i.e anemia; 31(31%) were suffering from three diseases i.e diabetes, hypertension and anemia ; and 6(6%) were suffering from four diseases i.e diabetes, hypertension, CAD and strokes.

It was found that in this study mean duration for which patient was undergoing dialysis was 5.28 yrs (SD 3.08) with minimum duration 1 year and maximum 14 yrs. Among the study subject 31(31%) underwent one dialysis per week, 47 (47%) underwent two dialysis per week and 22 (22%) underwent three dialysis per week.

according to HAM-A scale 45(45%), 16(16%), 11(11%) and 28(28%) study subjects were suffering from mild, mild to moderate, moderate to severe and severe to very severe anxiety respectively with mean HAM-A score 21.11 (SD 12.73).

Table 2: Relationship between Socio-demographic factors and Dialysis related factors and HAM-D and HAM-A Scale (p value)(ANOVA)

Factors	HAM-D Scale	HAM-A Scale
Gender	0.218	0.226
Residence	0.812	0.666
Marital Status	0.958	0.948
Education	0.480	0.584
Family Income	0.000	0.000
Family Type	0.000	0.000
Number Of Co-morbidity	0.000	0.000
Duration Of CKD	0.000	0.000
Number Of Dialysis Per Week	0.002	0.002

As shown in the table on doing one way ANOVA between gender, residence, marital status and educational level of study subject vs HAM-D showed no significant relationship with p value 0.218, 0.812, 0.958 and 0.480 respectively. The same factors vs HAM-A also did not show

significant relationship with p value 0.226, 0.666, 0.948 and 0.584 respectively.

But one way ANOVA between family income, family type, number of co-morbidity, duration of CKD and number of dialysis per week vs HAM-D showed significant relationship with p value < 0.001. (Figure 1 and 2)

Figure 1. Means Plot showing relationship between Duration of CKD and HAM-D Score

Figure 2. Means Plot showing relationship between Number of Dialysis per week and HAM-D Score

One way ANOVA between family income, family type, number of co-morbidity, duration of CKD and number of dialysis per week vs HAM-A showed significant relationship with p value <0.001.(Figure 3 and 4)

Figure 3. Means Plot showing relationship between family income and HAM-A Score

Figure 4. Means Plot showing relationship between duration of CKD and HAM-A Score

Discussion

Chronic Kidney disease prevalence is increasing in a good pace and so is the requirement for dialysis. Initially patient undergo occasional dialysis which later on progress to a once, twice or thrice dialysis per week. Various socio demographic factors and dialysis related factors affect the mental health of CKD patients. So this study was planned to study the psychiatric morbidity of CKD patients and to study their associated factors.

In this study of selected 100 CKD patients on hemodialysis the mean age was 50.05 yrs (SD 10.32) with 65 (65%) males and 35 (35%) females. The male to female ratio was 1.86:1. In this study 83 (83%), 8 (8%), 4(4%) and 5(5%) subjects were married, unmarried, divorcee and widower respectively and 66 (66%) subjects had their residence in rural area and rest 34(34%) had their residence in urban area. Educational level showed 15(15%), 47(47%), 25(25%) and 13(13%) were illiterate, attained education up-to primary level, secondary level and college level respectively. In this 52(52%) study subject lived in the nuclear family and 48(48%) lived in joint family.

Regarding family income 35(35%), 37(37%), 13(13%) and 15(15%) of the study had family income < Rs 10000, 10001-50000, 50001-100000 and > 100000 respectively. In this study most of the study subject i.e 35(35%) were suffering from two diseases i.e diabetes and hypertension and rest 7(7%) had no co-morbidity; 21(21%) were suffering from single disease i.e anemia; 31(31%) were suffering from three diseases i.e diabetes, hypertension and anemia; and 6(6%) were suffering from four diseases i.e diabetes, hypertension, CAD and strokes.

It was found that in this study mean duration for which patient was undergoing dialysis was 5.28 yrs (SD 3.08) with minimum duration 1 year and maximum 14 yrs. Among the study subject 31(31%) underwent one dialysis per week, 47 (47%) underwent two dialysis per week and 22 (22%) underwent three dialysis per week.

In this study 24(24%) were not suffering from any depression and rest 30(30%), 13(13%), 21(21%) and 12(12%) study subjects were suffering from mild, moderate, severe and very severe depression respectively with mean HAM-D score 14.10(SD

6.69). Similarly 45(45%), 16(16%), 11(11%) and 28(28%) study subjects were suffering from mild, mild to moderate, moderate to severe and severe to very severe anxiety respectively with mean HAM-A score 21.11 (SD 12.73).

In this study gender, residence, marital status and educational level of study subject vs HAM-D showed no significant relationship with p value 0.218, 0.812, 0.958 and 0.480 respectively. The same factors vs HAM-A also did not show significant relationship with p value 0.226, 0.666, 0.948 and 0.584 respectively.

But one way ANOVA between family income, family type, number of co-morbidity, duration of CKD and number of dialysis per week vs HAM-D showed significant relationship with p value < 0.001. The same above factors vs HAM-A showed significant relationship with p value <0.001.

In a study by Alshelleh et al [11] in 2023 on CKD patients mean duration of CKD was 10.4 years and in this study mean duration was 5.28 yrs (SD 3.08). They reported 61(92.4%) patients found to have depression with female has significant higher depression compared to males (p<0.05). In our study depression was prevalent in 76% (76) of CKD patient of varying degree in male and female and not significant. (p>0.05). Single patient has significant higher anxiety score compared to married (p<0.05) whereas in our study no relation of marriage and HAM-A or HAM-D score was found (p>0.05).

In a cross-sectional study done by Abdullah et al [12] in 2021 on CKD patients it was found that diabetes mellitus was present in 101 (56.1%) of patients and hypertension was present in 23 (12.8%) of the patients. In our study diabetes and hypertension was present in 72% (72) of the CKD patients. Among the patients, 2 (1.1 %), 112 (62.25%) and 66 (36.7%) on once weekly, twice weekly and thrice weekly dialysis. In our study the corresponding values were 31(31%), 47 (47%) and 22 (22%) respectively. Mean duration of dialysis was 9.01 years (SD 5.63 yrs) which in our study was 5.28 yrs (SD 3.08). About 27 patients (15.0 %) had depressive illness which in our study was present in 76% ranging from mild to very severe.

Vermani et al [13] in 2020 in a similar study found that psychiatric morbidity was present in 42(24.7%) patients s major depressive episode was most common (n = 37). In our study depression was present in 76% of the population. They also did not found any significant association between gender and marital status similar to our study. Similar to our study they also found significant positive association of duration of renal illness and duration of dialysis with psychiatric illness (P < 0.05) assessed by HAM-A and HAM-D. The presence of nonrenal comorbidities also had a

significant association with psychiatric illness (P < 0.005). In our study too those with having more number of comorbidities are significantly positively correlated with HAM-A and HAM-D.

In a study by Kumar et al [14] in 2018 on CKD patient undergoing HD it was found that depressive disorder was higher in males (p>0.05) and the anxiety was higher in males (p<0.05) but no such relationship was there in our study. Similar to our study they did not found affect of residence on depression score. They found depression and marriage were correlated but not anxiety and marriage. But in our study both depression and anxiety was not significantly related to marital status (p>0.05). Overall there was no relationship between education and depression or anxiety which is similar to our study. Similarly, income had no relationship with depression but had some relationship with anxiety. In our study low income was related to higher HAM-A and HAM-D score (p <0.05). The family type had no relationship with depression and anxiety among patients undergoing hemodialysis but in our study patient living in joint family had lower HAM-A and HAM-D score which stress upon the social support in improving mental health. When looked at the relationship between duration of CKD or hemodialysis and depression or anxiety, no relationship was found, but in our study more duration of CKD was associated with higher HAM-A and HAM-D score (p<0.05).

Nayana et al [15] in 2017 found mean score of Ham-D and HAM-A scale as 14.10(SD 6.69) and 21.11 (SD 12.73) respectively. The mean score of physical, mental and kidney disease components based on sociodemographic and clinical variables of respondents like age, gender, marital status, duration and frequency of dialysis and insurance distribution of study population did not showed statistically significant association. In our study age, gender and marital status did not show any relationship but duration, frequency of dialysis and family income showed significant relationship.

In a study done by Ramasubramanian et al [16] in 2015 on CKD patient on HD it was found that majority of the patients (n=113, 86.92%) had undergone dialysis for <5 years and in our study the mean duration of dialysis was 5.28 yrs (SD 3.08) . Most of the CKD patients diagnosed major depressive episode 17 (13.1%) followed by mild depressive episode 10 (7.7%) where as in our study 24(24%), 30(30%), 13(13%), 21(21%) and 12(12%) study subjects are not suffering from depression, suffering from mild, moderate, severe and very severe depression respectively. They reported that majority of the patients (n=76, 58.46%) were currently unemployed among which 40 patients (30.76%) were diagnosed with mental illness and in our study low family income was

significantly affecting HAM-A and HAM-D score ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion

This study revealed that significant number of CKD patients on hemodialysis were suffering from depression and anxiety. This study found that presence of depression and presence of anxiety were overall affected with low family income and living in nuclear family which stress upon lack of social and economic support affecting them. Even having more number of co-morbid disease, more duration of CKD and more number of dialysis per week were also affecting the mental health. So even mental health of CKD patients on HD must be taken care of along with dialysis.

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